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Quantum Chemical Calculations on A Dopamine Derivative

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A semi rigorous calculation by CNDO/2 method¹ is presented on the minimum energy conformation of protonated 5-hydroxy dopamine (5-HDA). 5-HDA (Fig. 1) has been shown to be a new 'false' sympathetic transmitter². The theoretical conformation of this molecule has been studied recently³ by the PCIO method⁴.

Fig. 1

Fig. 1. The (nonstandard) numbering system used for 5-hydroxydopamine molecule.

Fig. 2. 5-Hydroxydopamine: gross atomic populations--CNDO/2 and PCIO (within the parentheses).

The starting atomic coordinates were taken from crystallographic data⁵ and the total molecular energy for various conformations was calculated by allowing rotations around C1-C7 and C7-C8 bonds respectively. The torsion angles at the minimum energy conformation are found to be :

$$\tau_1 (C6-C1-C7-C8) = 56^\circ$$

$$\tau_2 (C1-C7-C8-N^+) = 40^\circ$$

There are 60 valence electrons in this molecule and the electronic energy of 5-HDA converged in 7 iterations to -529.5486 a. u. ($E_{\text{total}} = -131.9389$ a. u.). The gross atomic populations in the CNDO method are the diagonal elements of the density matrix where the density matrix is defined as the sum of the squares of the coefficients C_{ri} times the occupation numbers of each MO ϕ_i summed over the basis atomic orbitals χ_r . These are presented in Fig. 2.

As a result of the zero differential overlap approximation, one cannot calculate a quantity formally analogous to a total overlap population by the CNDO method. It has been shown⁶ that one can use the off-diagonal elements, scaled appropriately, in a Mulliken population analysis to obtain an approximation to total overlap populations. These results are shown in Table 1 for the atoms which can be considered as bonded to one another. It is to be noted that these TOPs seem to be of the correct magnitude for bonded atoms and that all the figures for TOPs between bonded atoms are large, of the order of 0.95 for C-C bonds or 0.6 to 0.7 for C to an external substituent atom. TOPs between non-bonded atoms are only of the order of 0.001.

Total overlap populations are of great potential interest for conformational studies. It has been shown that the maximum of the index molecular total overlap population (the sum of all the total overlap population in a molecule) is usually a more sensitive criterion of the equilibrium geometry than the minimum of the calculated total energy, especially for less than *ab initio* molecular orbital calculations^{7,8}. This index turns out to be especially significant for large molecules⁷. MTOPs have been proved to be useful in predicting equilibrium geometries. The MTOP for the minimum

energy conformation of the protonated form of 5-HDA is : 17.98⁸.

TABLE 1—5-HYDROXY DOPAMINE : TOTAL OVERLAP POPULATIONS BETWEEN BONDED ATOMS—CNDO/2

Atoms	TOP
Cl-C2	0.9524
Cl-C6	0.9497
Cl-C7	0.7211
C2-C3	0.9594
C2-H2	0.7565
C3-C4	0.9588
C3-O1	0.6067
C4-C5	0.9520
C4-O2	0.5878
C5-C6	0.9540
C5-O3	0.6445
C6-H6	0.7543
C7-C8	0.7249
C7-H71	0.7000
C7-H72	0.7244
C8-N	0.5716
C8-H81	0.7201
C8-H82	0.7543
N-HN1	0.6810
N-HN2	0.6704
N-HN3	0.6477
O1-HO1	0.6446
O2-HO2	0.6271
O3-HO3	0.6692

It may be of interest to mention in this connection that the global minimum energy by PCILO method was obtained at $\tau_1 \approx 56^\circ$ and $\tau_2 \approx 40^\circ$ for :-HDA. The PCILO dipolemoment for this conformation is : 34.4858 D and agrees well with that of CNDO/2 value : 34.4995 D.

The gross atomic populations (GAP's) obtained by PCILO method are indicated within the parentheses (Fig. 2).

It is to be noted that the PCILO-GAP's more or less resemble the CNDO/2 results, and there is reasonable agreement between the CNDO/2 and PCILO GAP's on the N-atom. The positively-charged nitrogen in the side-chain ammonium group is one of the most active points for biological and pharmacological activities of the protonated molecules.

The work reported here represents a part of the work in progress. The allowed region for 6-hydroxy dopamine (6-HDA) has already been determined³ by PCILO method⁴. The CNDO/2 calculations on 6-HDA and its oxidation product (quinone form) are in progress. Quantum chemical calculations solve the conformational problems and charge distributions of 5-HDA and the biogenic amine NE (nor-epinephrine) can help to find a new insight into the mechanism of replacement of NE by this molecule (5-HDA). It has been shown² that 5-HDA may intrude into the pathways of NE.

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Some Newer Cyanoethylated Cyanoacetanilides as Possible Insecticides*

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THE studies on cyanoethylation reaction as reported earlier from the laboratory,^{1,2,3} have been further extended to synthesize some newer substituted cyanoethyl-cyanoacetanilides. In the present investigation these compounds have been tested for their insecticidal activity on adult housefly.

Experimental

Cyanoethylation of Cyanoacetanilides to α -cyano- α -bis-(β -cyanoethyl) acetanilides.

A mixture of cyanoacetanilide (2 g), dioxane (20 ml) and benzyltrimethylammonium hydroxide (1.3 ml) was stirred. Acrylonitrile (1.9 g) was added slowly with

*Contributed on 65th Birthday of Professor H. Kammerer, W. Germany.